

Thermodynamic study of formamide + ethylene glycol, +diethyleneglycol, +triethyleneglycol, +poly(ethyleneglycol)-200, +poly(ethyleneglycol)-300, +propyleneglycol and +poly(propyleneglycol)-1025 binary liquid mixtures at 35°

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Density and viscosity of pure formamide and its binary mixtures with ethyleneglycol, diethyleneglycol, triethyleneglycol, poly(ethyleneglycol)-200, poly(ethyleneglycol)-300, propyleneglycol and poly(propyleneglycol)-1025 have been measured as a function of composition over the entire range at 35°. The excess volume, excess viscosity, excess free energy of activation of viscous flow and interaction parameter of Grungberg and Nissan have been calculated from the experimental data as a function of composition. All the excess functions are found to be either negative or positive over the entire range of composition depending on the molecular interactions and the nature of liquid mixtures. These properties are discussed in terms of nature of the molecular interactions between component molecules.

The physicochemical properties of aqueous solutions of glycols have been extensively studied due to their high polar nature, and many industrial and pharmaceutical applications¹. But only few attempts² have been made in the direction of finding of interactions of these glycols in non-aqueous media.

Hence, an attempt has been made to study the behavior of formamide (FA) + ethyleneglycol (EG), +diethyleneglycol (DEG), +triethyleneglycol (TEG), +poly(ethyleneglycol)-200 (PEG-200), +poly(ethyleneglycol)-300 (PEG-300), +propyleneglycol (PG) and +poly(propyleneglycol)-1025 (PPG-1025) binary mixtures covering entire composition range. In order to provide insight into the structural consequences of intermolecular interactions, the solvent FA was chosen for the present study due to its unusual properties. Besides, FA is strongly self-associated through extensive networks of hydrogen bonds³ and also of its importance in the synthetic chemistry. Density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of these liquid mixtures have been measured at 35° and the excess volume (V^E), excess viscosity (η^E), excess free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) and interaction parameter of Grungberg and Nissan (d) were calculated.

Results and Discussion

The excess functions V^E , η^E and G^{*E} and d were calculated from the experimentally determined ρ and η using equations⁴ (1-4),

$$V^E = V - (X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2) \quad (1)$$

$$\eta^E = \eta - (X_1 \eta_1 + X_2 \eta_2) \quad (2)$$

$$G^{*E} = RT (\ln \eta V - X_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 - X_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2) \quad (3)$$

$$\ln \eta = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_1 X_2 d \quad (4)$$

where X , V and η represent mole fraction, molar volume and viscosity, respectively, and subscripts 1, 2 represent the pure components. The values are presented in Table 1 along with the values of ρ , η and mole fraction (X_2) of FA. The molar volume (V) of pure liquid/mixture is calculated using eqn. (5)

$$V = M/\rho \quad (5)$$

where M is the molecular weight and for mixture is given by $X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2$.

The observed negative values of V^E for FA + DEG, +TEG, +PEG-200, +PEG-300 and +PPG-1025 systems over the entire composition (Fig. 1), indicate that the main contribution to V^E is the decrease in volume due to hydrogen bond formation between unlike molecules⁵. There may be another source of negative contribution to V^E due to the difference in the size and shape of component molecules in the mixture. The molar volumes for pure components are calculated using eqn. (5). The values for FA is $40.19 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and that for DEG, TEG, PEG-200, PEG-300 and PPG-1025 are 95.98, 135.04, 179.77, 269.45 and $1031.30 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. Because of the much difference in the molar volumes of the components, FA molecules will fit into the structures of the glycol molecules thereby reducing the volume of the mixture⁶. This is the

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η), excess viscosity (η^E), volume (V), excess volume (V^E), excess free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}), interaction parameter (d) and mole fraction of formamide (X_2) with EG, DEG, TEG, PEG-200, PEG-300, PG and PPG-1025 at 35°

X_2	$\times 10^{-3} \rho$ kg m ⁻³	$\times 10^3 \eta$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$\times 10^3 \eta^E$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$\times 10^5 V$ m ³ mol ⁻¹	$\times 10^6 V^E$ m ³ mol ⁻¹	$\times 10^5 G^{*E}$ J mol ⁻¹	d
FA + EG							
0.0000	1.10307	10.591	0.00	56.27	0.00	0.00	-
0.1039	1.10392	8.974	-0.73	54.62	0.02	7.54	0.0757
0.2093	1.10485	7.534	-1.26	52.95	0.05	10.42	0.0445
0.3128	1.10580	6.345	-1.56	51.31	0.07	12.67	0.0356
0.4228	1.10722	5.295	-1.67	49.56	0.08	15.19	0.0394
0.5198	1.10861	4.509	-1.62	48.00	0.09	16.04	0.0407
0.6248	1.11046	3.779	-1.45	46.31	0.09	14.46	0.0346
0.7249	1.11258	3.191	-1.18	44.69	0.08	11.60	0.0270
0.8215	1.11525	2.715	-0.83	43.11	0.05	8.85	0.0302
0.9214	1.11817	2.298	-0.39	41.48	0.02	5.35	0.0517
1.0000	1.12060	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.00	0.00	-
FA + DEG							
0.0000	1.10557	17.588	0.00	95.99	0.00	0.00	-
0.1121	1.10721	16.138	0.30	89.66	-0.07	114.27	1.5793
0.2180	1.10885	14.995	0.80	83.69	-0.13	224.29	1.8391
0.3119	1.11035	13.897	1.17	78.42	-0.17	312.66	2.0559
0.4138	1.11212	12.401	1.26	72.69	-0.20	386.23	2.2609
0.5202	1.11375	10.589	1.11	66.75	-0.21	435.38	2.4849
0.6153	1.11518	8.932	0.93	61.46	-0.19	457.62	2.7776
0.7049	1.11647	7.318	0.71	56.49	-0.17	450.71	3.1371
0.8180	1.11821	5.499	0.65	50.22	-0.12	414.26	4.1120
0.9052	1.11959	3.946	0.46	45.40	-0.08	311.58	5.4709
1.0000	1.12064	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.00	0.00	-
FA + TEG							
0.0000	1.11209	23.841	0.00	135.03	0.00	0.00	-
0.1170	1.11338	22.339	1.05	123.83	-0.11	171.20	2.1721
0.2119	1.11445	20.858	1.64	114.76	-0.18	296.81	2.3389
0.3139	1.11542	19.018	2.03	105.05	-0.22	416.33	2.5565
0.4265	1.11643	16.777	2.25	94.35	-0.24	527.93	2.8773
0.5518	1.11756	14.118	2.32	82.46	-0.23	622.64	3.4014
0.6514	1.11850	11.588	1.97	73.03	-0.22	652.14	3.9200
0.7606	1.11943	8.502	1.27	62.72	-0.18	615.72	4.6714
0.8343	1.12005	6.473	0.85	55.76	-0.14	543.25	5.5037
0.9307	1.12047	3.797	0.28	46.70	-0.06	325.36	7.2131
1.0000	1.12064	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.00	0.00	-
FA + PEG-200							
0.0000	1.11243	28.066	0.00	179.79	0.00	0.00	-
0.1148	1.11452	26.731	1.66	163.49	-0.27	202.68	2.4998
0.2148	1.11612	24.987	2.52	149.37	-0.43	359.30	2.6698
0.3320	1.11741	22.384	2.97	132.94	-0.49	517.40	2.9280
0.4489	1.11871	19.627	3.26	116.60	-0.53	652.59	3.3397
0.5348	1.11963	17.487	3.36	104.61	-0.51	733.00	3.7674
0.6474	1.12076	14.168	2.97	88.94	-0.47	789.85	4.4848
0.7489	1.12189	10.768	2.22	74.83	-0.41	773.05	5.4081

Note

Table-1(contd.)

0.8173	1.12214	8.419	1.65	65.37	-0.33	712.75	6.3706
0.9471	1.12202	3.857	0.47	47.45	-0.13	367.16	10.2362
1.0000	1.12064	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.00	0.00	-
FA + PEG-300							
0.0000	1.11328	41.336	0.00	269.47	0.00	0.00	-
0.1148	1.11516	40.789	3.97	242.77	-0.38	274.35	3.2858
0.2149	1.11659	39.517	6.63	219.61	-0.59	495.57	3.5858
0.3258	1.11767	37.184	8.66	194.09	-0.68	717.32	4.0043
0.4438	1.11878	33.458	9.57	167.02	-0.71	916.64	4.5811
0.5597	1.11988	28.948	9.62	140.46	-0.68	1071.70	5.4237
0.6641	1.12081	24.147	8.93	116.60	-0.61	1161.62	6.5943
0.7817	1.12191	18.064	7.47	89.76	-0.49	1178.49	9.0035
0.8702	1.12237	12.097	4.98	69.62	-0.34	1044.33	12.4216
0.9640	1.12188	4.628	1.20	48.33	-0.12	515.38	20.9126
1.0000	1.12064	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.00	0.00	-
FA + PG							
0.0000	1.02617	25.461	0.00	74.16	0.00	0.00	-
0.1139	1.03160	20.528	-2.26	70.34	0.05	55.59	0.7323
0.2193	1.03739	16.387	-3.93	66.79	0.08	89.38	0.6792
0.3257	1.04411	12.879	-4.94	63.20	0.10	113.36	0.6629
0.4428	1.05263	9.478	-5.60	59.23	0.11	111.92	0.5526
0.5424	1.06095	7.290	-5.45	55.85	0.11	107.46	0.5109
0.6584	1.07221	5.443	-4.58	51.90	0.10	107.56	0.5745
0.753	1.08289	4.129	-3.67	48.68	0.09	81.68	0.5009
0.8552	1.09647	3.008	-2.40	45.18	0.07	39.30	0.2901
0.9458	1.11059	2.419	-0.86	42.07	0.04	37.08	0.9380
1.0000	1.12960	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.00	0.00	-
FA + PPG-1025							
0.0000	0.99389	82.328	0.00	1031.30	0.00	0.00	-
0.1148	0.99523	81.785	8.68	916.87	-0.64	413.14	4.1302
0.2125	0.99664	79.489	14.23	819.51	-1.18	743.29	4.5061
0.3208	0.99840	77.859	21.30	711.77	-1.58	1105.80	5.2116
0.4159	1.00002	76.289	27.37	617.42	-1.67	1411.50	6.0444
0.5348	1.00248	71.248	31.87	499.68	-1.57	1746.74	7.4020
0.6323	1.00506	64.845	33.30	403.33	-1.29	1973.37	9.0730
0.7418	1.00989	53.484	30.74	295.15	-0.95	2130.77	12.1308
0.8378	1.01890	37.556	22.52	200.21	-0.74	2085.63	17.1192
0.9442	1.04719	13.347	6.86	95.23	-0.27	1450.33	32.0153
1.0000	1.12064	2.009	0.00	40.19	0.000	0.00	-

reason for higher negative values for higher molecular weight glycols. Muller⁷ made a similar report from the V^E studies of binary liquid mixtures.

The observed positive values of V^E for the mixtures FA + EG and FA + PG over the entire composition range (Fig. 1), indicate the mutual dissociation of the component molecules. Because of the less difference in the molar volumes of the components (EG 56.27×10^{-5} and PG 70.16×10^{-5} m³

mol⁻¹), FA molecules will not fit into the structures of EG and PG thereby increases the volume of the mixture.

A correlation between the signs of η^E and V^E has been observed for a number of binary solvent systems⁸, i.e. if η^E is positive then V^E is negative and vice versa. In the present observation this is found to hold good (Fig. 2).

The variation of G^{*E} is positive for all the systems under study over the entire composition range (Fig. 3). This is

Fig. 1. Plots of excess volume vs mole fraction of formamide : (○) EG, (●) DEG, (Δ) TEG, (▲) PEG-200, (□) PEG-300, (■) PG, (★) PPG-1025.

Fig. 2. Plots of excess viscosity vs mole fraction of formamide : (○) EG, (●) DEG, (Δ) TEG, (▲) PEG-200, (□) PEG-300, (■) PG, (★) PPG-1025.

Fig. 3. Plots of excess free energy of activation of viscous flow vs mole fraction of formamide : (○) EG, (●) DEG, (Δ) TEG, (▲) PEG-200, (□) PEG-300, (■) PG, (★) PPG-1025.

due to the nature of complex formation between the components. Subha *et al.*⁴ made a similar observation from their G^*E studies for the mixtures of propionic acid and alcohols. The positive d values for the systems under study supports the presence of strong interactions⁹ between the components.

Experimental

FA (Sd. Fine, A.R.) was used as such. EG, DEG, TEG, PEG-200, PEG-300 (Sd. Fine, A.R.), PG and PPG-1025 (Spectrochem, India) were used after purification¹⁰. All the samples were kept over 4 Å molecular sieves to reduce water content and protect from atmospheric moisture and carbon dioxide.

Solvent mixtures were prepared by weight method. Density was determined with an accuracy of $\pm 0.0002 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ with help of double-walled pycnometer at $35 \pm 0.01^\circ$. The viscosity was obtained with an accuracy of $\pm 0.005 \text{ Cp}$ using a suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer. Densities of pure liquids agree well with the literature values^{4,7,11}.

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